

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ
JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

ДАВРИЙЛИГИ: 2016-2026

ЖИЛД 11
СОҢ 1

2026

ЧОП
ЭТИЛГАН САНА:
06.02.2026

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

11 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 11, НОМЕР 1

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 11, ISSUE 1

Бош мухаррир:

Ризаев Жасур Алимжанович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети ректори
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Ўзбекистон Республикаси
Фанлар академиясининг Иммунология ва инсон
геномикаси институти директор ўринбосари,
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Масъул котиб:

Самиева Гулноза Утқуровна
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Нашр учун масъул:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
онкология кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

ТАХРИРИЯТ КЕНГАШИ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна
*Иммунология ва инсон геномикаси институти директори –
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Ўзбекистон
Республикаси Фанлар академияси академиги*

Jin Young Choi
*Сеул миллий университети Стоматология мактаби оғиз ва
юз-жағ жарроҳлиги департаменти профессори, Жанубий
Кореянинг юз-жағ ва эстетик жарроҳлик ассоциацияси
президенти*

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаматовна
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Самарқанд
давлат тиббиёт университети проректори, 1-клиникаси бош
врачи. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Самарқанд
давлат тиббиёт университети Гистология, цитология ва
эмбриология кафедраси мудири
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович
*тиббиёт фандар доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети болалар жарроҳлиги кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент давлат тиббиёт
университети Оилавий тиббиётда акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси профессори ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Очилов Улугбек Усмонович
*DSc, доцент, СамДТУ Дипломдан кейинги таълим
факултети Психиатрия курси мудири. СамДТУ Илмий
кенгаши котиби. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>*

Шавази Наргиз Нуралiena
*DSc. Доцент, СамДМУ 3-сон акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси мудири <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>*

Юлдашев Равшан Захидович
*Тожикистон Давлат тиббиёт университети Онкология
ва нур таъхиси кафедраси мудири, Тиббиёт фанлари
доктори, Профессор. Душанбе, Тожикистон.
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>*

Саидов Сандамир Абборович
*тиббиёт фанлар доктори,
Тошкент фармацевтика институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Бабалданов Ойбек Абдуҷаббарович
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент давлат тиббиёт
университети, Тери-таносил болалар тери-таносил
касаликлари ва ОИТС кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Тошкент
педиатрия тиббиёт институти Факультет болалар
хирургия кафедраси. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327*

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
№2-сон Педиатрия, неонатология ва болалар
касаликлари пропедевтикаси кафедраси доценти.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
Тошкент давлат тиббиёт университети
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети, онкология кафедраси профессори
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Даминов Феруз Асадуллаевич
*Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
2-сон Даволаш факультети декани,
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент.
Самарқанд, Ўзбекистон.*

Миржурев Элбек Миршавкатович
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
ЎзССВ Тиббий ходимларни касбий малакасини
ривожлантириши марказининг Нейрореабилитация
кафедраси мудири, Тошкент, Ўзбекистон*

Тагаев Шерқабул Бойқабдулович
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, хирургия кафедраси
доценти Тошкент давлат тиббиёт университети.
ORCID: 0009-0004-7661-9253.*

Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналлов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Главный редактор:

Ризаев Жасур Алимджанович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ректор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0001-5468-9403

Заместитель главного редактора:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
доктор медицинских наук, Заместитель директора Института иммунологии и геномики человека Академии наук Республики Узбекистан, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-3933

Ответственный секретарь:

Самиева Гульноза Уткуровна
доктор медицинских наук, профессор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-6142-7054

Ответственный за публикацию:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, доцент кафедры онкологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-0888-9150

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

директор Института иммунологии и геномики человека доктор медицинских наук, профессор, академик АН РУз

Jin Young Choi

профессор департамента оральной и челюстно-лицевой хирургии школы стоматологии Стоматологического госпиталя Сеульского национального университета, Президент Корейского общества челюстно-лицевой и эстетической хирургии

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаматовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, проректор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, заведующий кафедрой Гистологии, цитологии и эмбриологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-0615-0144

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Детской хирургии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-2650-4445

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

Доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры акушерства и гинекологии Семейной медицины Ташкентский государственный медицинский университет **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9313-4918

Очилов Улугбек Усманович

DSc, доцент, заведующий курсом психиатрии факультета постдипломного образования СамГМУ. Секретарь Ученого совета СамГМУ. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>

Шавази Наргиз Нуралиевна

DSc, доцент, заведующая кафедрой акушерства и гинекологии N 3 СамГМУ. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>

Юлдашев Рашид Захидович

Заведующий кафедрой Онкологии и лучевой диагностики Таджикского медицинского университета, д.м.н., профессор Душанбе, Таджикистан <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>

Сандов Сандамир Аброрович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский фармацевтический институт **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-6616-5428

Бабаджанов Ойбек Абдужаббарович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский государственный медицинский университет, доцент кафедры Дерматовенерология, детская дерматовенерология и СПИД, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-3022-916X

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Факультетской детской хирургии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-5409-4327

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии, неонатологии и перепродукции детских болезней №2 Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергатовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор Ташкентский государственный медицинский университет **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры онкологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета **ORCID ID:** 0000-0001-5272-5503

Даминов Феруз Асадуллаевич

Декан лечебного факультета №2 Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, доктор медицинских наук, доцент. Самарканд, Узбекистан.

Мирджураев Эльбек Миршавкатович

Заведующий кафедрой Нейрореабилитации Центра развития профессиональной квалификации медицинских работников МЗ РУз, д.м.н., профессор Ташкент, Узбекистан

Тагаев Шеркабул Бойкабулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры хирургии, Ташкентский государственный медицинский университет. **ORCID:** 0009-0004-7661-9253.

Верстка: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Chief Editor:

Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich
MD, DSc, Professor of Dental Medicine,
Rector of the Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Deputy Chief Editor:

Ziyadullaev Shukhrat Khudayberdievich
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Deputy Director of the Institute
of Immunology and Human Genomics of the Academy of
Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Responsible secretary:

Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna
doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Responsible for publication:

Shakhanova Shakhnoza Shavkatovna
PhD, Docent Department of Oncology
Samarkand State medical university
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

EDITORIAL BOARD:

Aripova Tamara Uktamovna

*Director of the Institute of Immunology and Human Genomics -
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Academician of the
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan*

Jin Young Choi

*Professor Department of Oral and Maxillofacial
Surgery School of Dentistry Dental Hospital
Seoul National University, President of the
Korean Society of Maxillofacial Aesthetic Surgery*

Abdullaeva Nargiza Nurmatovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Vice-Rector
Samarkand State Medical University, Chief Physician of
the 1st Clinic ORCID ID: 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Oripov Firdavs Suratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Head of the Department of Histology, Cytology and
Embryology of Samarkand State Medical University.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Mavlyanov Farkhod Shavkatovich

*Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of Pediatric
Surgery, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Magzumova Nargiza Makhamovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department
of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Family Medicine, Tashkent State
Medical University. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Ochilov Ulugbek Usmanovich

*DSc, Docent, Head of the Psychiatry Course at the Faculty of
Postgraduate Education of SamSMU. Secretary of the Academic
Council of SamSMU. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>*

Shavazi Nargiz Nuraliyena

*DSc, Associate Professor, Head of the Department of Obstetrics
and Gynecology N 3 of Samarkand State Medical University.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>*

Yuldashev Ravshan Zakhidovich

*Head of the Department of Oncology and Radiation Diagnostics
at Tajik State Medical University, Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor. Dushanbe, Tajikistan <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>*

Saidov Saidamir

*Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute,
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Babadjanov Oybek Abdujabbarovich

*Doctor of sciences in medicine, Tashkent State
Medical University, Docent the Department of
Dermatovenerology, pediatric dermatovenerology
and AIDS, ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute,
Faculty of Children Department of Surgery.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

Yuldashev Botir Akhmatovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
Pediatrics, Neonatology and Propaedeutics of Pediatrics,
Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ibragimova Malika Xudayberganovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Tashkent State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Rahimov Nodir Maxammatkulovich

*DSc, Professor of Oncology,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Daminov Feruz Asadullaevich

*Dean of the Faculty of Medicine No. 2, Samarkand State
Medical University, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate
Professor. Samarkand, Uzbekistan.*

Mirjuraev Elbek Mirshavkatovich

*Head of the Department of Neurorehabilitation Center
for the development of professional qualification of
medical workers, Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor. Tashkent, Uzbekistan
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-2111-4388>*

Tagaev Sher Kabul Baykabulovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor
of Surgery Department, Tashkent State Medical University
ORCID: 0009-0004-7661-9253.*

Page Maker: Khurshid Mirzakhmedov

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY

1. **Matlubov Mansur Muratovich, Muminov Abduhalim Abduvakil, Khudoyberdieva Gulrukh Sobirovna, Umarova Bibikhonum Azimjon kizi**
EFFECTIVENESS OF POSTOPERATIVE INTENSIVE THERAPY IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH VARICOSE VEINS.....12

NEUROLOGY, PSYCHIATRY

2. **Mansurova Nargiza Asrorovna**
DIAGNOSTIC VALUE OF INFLAMMATORY PROCESSES IN DIFFERENTIATING PARKINSONISM SUBTYPES.....18
3. **Tulyaganova Nodirakhon Malikovna.**
EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENTAL DISORDERS IN CHILDREN BORN FROM CONSANGUINEOUS MARRIAGES.....26
4. **Ochilov Ulug'bek Usmanovich, Turaev Bobir Temirpulotovich, Sultanov Shoxrux Khabibullaevich**
CORRECTION OF DEPRESSIVE DISORDERS AND EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF COMPREHENSIVE REHABILITATION IN PATIENTS WITH CHEMICAL ADDICTIVE DISORDERS.....34
5. **Turaev Bobir Temirpulotovich, Sultanov Shoxrux Khabibullaevich**
FACTORS INFLUENCING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MEDICAL AND SOCIAL REHABILITATION IN PATIENTS WITH CHEMICAL ADDICTIVE DISORDERS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....41
6. **Khakimova Sakhiba Ziyadulloyevna, Gaffarova Parvina Abdurafikovna**
ETIOPATHOGENETIC SIGNIFICANCE OF MAO-B INHIBITORS IN PARKINSON'S DISEASE AND THEIR ROLE IN REDUCING MOTOR SYMPTOMS.....48
7. **Mirzhuraev Elbek Mirshavkatovich, Adambaev Zufar Ibragimovich, Mamatkhanova Charos Bahodirovna**
STRATIFICATION OF MANAGEMENT FOR PATIENTS WITH COMBINED VERTEBROGENIC PATHOLOGY AND PELVIC ORGAN DYSFUNCTION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY APPROACH.....55
8. **Rogov Alexey Vladimirovich, Lipartiya Mary Givievna**
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SEVERITY OF PARANOID SCHIZOPHRENIA IN PATIENTS WITH AUTOAGGRESSIVE MANIFESTATIONS IN THE EARLY PERIOD OF THE DISEASE.....63

MORPHOLOGY

9. **Kiyomov Ikhtiyor Ergashevich, Islamov Shavkat Erjigitovich**
MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE THYMUS DURING ACUTE EXPOSURE TO A DEFOLIANT.....69

ONCOLOGY

10. **Abdikarimov Azizbek Khurshidjon ugli, Yusupbekov Abrorbek Akhmedjanovich, Usmonov Begzod Boymatovich, Xasanov Akbar Ibroximovich**
HUMAN PAPILLOMAVIRUS AND OROPHARYNGEAL CANCER: CURRENT CLINICAL-EPIDEMIOLOGICAL AND PROGNOSTIC ASPECTS (REVIEW).....77

11. **Iskandarova Shakhnoza Tulkinovna, Khakimova Laylo Nuraliyevna, Yusupov Anvar Sobirovich**
STUDY OF THE DYNAMICS OF PROLACTIN AND GLUCOSE LEVELS IN PATIENTS WITH GASTRIC CANCER DURING THE PERIOPERATIVE PERIOD UNDER COMBINED EPIDURAL ANESTHESIA.....89
12. **Rakhmatov Dilshod Bakhridinovich**
EVALUATION OF RADIATION DOSE LOAD TO ORGANS AT RISK WHEN SWITCHING TO A HYPOFRACTIONATED REGIMEN OF POSTOPERATIVE RADIOTHERAPY FOR LEFT BREAST CANCER.....95
13. **Shernazarov Otamurod Narmuratovich**
ACOUSTIC ANALYSIS OF VOICE FUNCTION IN PATIENTS WITH BENIGN LARYNGEAL LESIONS.....101
14. **Ten Vladimir Denisovich, Alimov Ijod Rustamovich, Umarov Rustam Dilshodovich.**
OUR EXPERIENCE OF PERCUTANEOUS BIOPSY IN METASTATIC LESIONS OF THE LUMBAR SPINE.....105
15. **Umarov Rustam Dilshodovich, Alimov Ijod Rustamovich, Ten Vladimir Denisovich.**
ISOLATED LATERAL SURGICAL APPROACH FOR VERTEBRAL BODY TUMORS WITH EXTRADURAL INTRACANAL INVASION AT TH11–L2.....109
16. **Ismailov Avaz Alisherovich, Umarov Rustam Dilshodovich, Alimov Ijod Rustamovich,**
POSTERIOR DECOMPRESSIVE AND STABILIZING APPROACH FOR THORACIC AND LUMBAR VERTEBRAL BODY TUMORS WITH INTRACANAL EXTENSION.116
17. **Umarov Rustam Dilshodovich, Alimov Ijod Rustamovich, Ten Vladimir Denisovich**
ISOLATED LATERAL SURGICAL APPROACH FOR VERTEBRAL BODY TUMORS WITH EXTRADURAL INTRACANAL INVASION AT TH11–L2 LEVELS.....121
18. **Sharopov Sadullo Shukurillovich**
CORRELATION BETWEEN ELECTROENCEPHALOGRAPHIC CHANGES AND MRI CHARACTERISTICS IN PATIENTS WITH BRAIN TUMORS.....129

MEDICAL REHABILITATION

19. **Raimkulova Dilnoza Farkhaddinovna**
PROGNOSTIC CRITERIA AND ANALYSIS OF PHYSICAL PERFORMANCE IN ADOLESCENTS ENGAGED IN DIFFERENT TYPES OF SPORTS.....135
20. **Mamatkhanova Charos Bahodirovna**
STRATIFICATION OF SURGICAL AND REHABILITATION TREATMENT FOR POST-TRAUMATIC MYELOPATHIES AT THE CERVICAL AND THORACIC SPINE LEVELS.....142
21. **Mamatkhanova Charos Bahodirovna**
ANALYSIS OF PATIENTS WITH SPINAL PATHOLOGY AND SPINAL CORD DISEASES AT THE REPUBLICAN CENTER FOR REHABILITATION OF DISABLED PERSONS.....149
22. **Tukhtaev Firdavs Mukhitdinovich, Kadirov Jonibek Fayzullayevich**
THE IMPACT OF MINERAL AND ACID–BASE METABOLIC CORRECTION ON POSTOPERATIVE REHABILITATION IN CHILDREN WITH UROLITHIASIS.....155

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

23. **Boymurodov Shukhrat Abdujalilovich, Kurbanov Yoqubjon Khamdamovich, Yusupov Shokhrukh Shuhratovich, Djurayev Jamolbek Abdukakharovich, Soatov Ilyosjon Olimovich**
SIGNIFICANCE OF IL10 RS1800872, SERPINE1 RS1799768, NOS3 RS2070744, AND IL1B RS1143627 GENE POLYMORPHISMS IN PURULENT-NECROTIC PROCESSES OF THE MAXILLOFACIAL REGION.....160

24. **Alyavi Mufassal Nasirkhanovna, Khaydarov Artur Mikhaylovich, Alieva Muattar Abdulkhayevna**
COMPLEX TREATMENT OF CHRONIC GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS IN PATIENTS WITH STABLE ANGINA PECTORIS.....171
25. **Ismoilov Mirkamol Xusan o'g'li Nigmatova Iroda Maratovna**
THE ROLE OF VITAMIN D IN THE CONDITION OF PERIODONTAL TISSUES DURING ORTHODONTIC TREATMENT IN PREGNANT WOMEN.....180
26. **Irgashev Shokhrukh Khasanovich**
ANALYSIS OF THE HYGIENIC INDICATORS OF THE ORAL MUCOSA OF PERSONS WHO HAVE UNDERGONE ORTHOPEDIC STOMATOLOGICAL TREATMENT.....190
27. **Ibragimova Malika Khudaiberganovna, Abduvahobova Dilnoza Anvarovna**
CLINICAL AND DIAGNOSTIC ASPECTS OF RED FLAT AND DEPRESSED ORAL MUCOSA.....196
28. **Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich, Akhmedova Sayyora Mukhamadovna, Absalamova Nigora Fakhriddinovna**
IMPROVEMENT OF TREATMENT STRATEGIES FOR ORAL MUCOSAL LEUKOPLAKIA BASED ON IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL RESULTS.....204
29. **Otkhonova Mohinog Ganiyon qizi, Khramova Natalya Vladimirovna, Gafurov Zafar Atkhamovich**
JUSTIFICATION OF MAXILLARY RECONSTRUCTION USING A TIBIAL BONE AUTOGRAFT.....212
30. **Madazimov Madamin Muminovich, Turaev Feruz Fakhtullaevich, Yusufovna Mohamed Khava, Pustovetova Maria Gennadievna, Akramova Nozima Akramovna**
CELL-ASSISTED LIPOTRANSFER IN THE CORRECTION OF AESTHETIC AND POST-TRAUMATIC DEFORMITIES OF FACIAL SOFT TISSUES.....219

TRAUMATOLOGY

31. **Axtamov A'zam, Axtamov Azim**
STUDYING THE RESULTS OF RECONSTRUCTIVE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF COMBINED MENISCLE WOUNDS.....228
32. **Axtamov Azim, Axtamov A'zam**
DIAGNOSIS AND MODERN METHODS OF TREATMENT OF ACETABULUM INJURIES (LITERATURE REVIEW).....233
33. **Axtamov A'zam, Axtamov Azim**
EXPERIENCE IN TREATING INTRA-ARTICULAR FRACTURES OF THE DISTAL PART OF THE HUMERUS IN CHILDREN.....241
34. **Davirov Sharof Majidovich, Urinbaev Payzilla Urinbaevich, Mansurov Djalolidin Shamsidinovich**
OSTEOPLASTIC RECONSTRUCTION OF EXTENSIVE DIAPHYSEAL LONG BONE DEFECTS USING EXTERNAL FIXATION DEVICES.....246

PEDIATRICS

35. **Choliev Matyoqub Sulaymanovich, Khotamov Khusniddin Narzullayevich, Tilavov O'ktam Khamrayevich**
SOFT TISSUE NECROSIS IN CHILDREN: CLINICAL FEATURES, DIAGNOSIS AND PRINCIPLES OF TREATMENT.....256
36. **Umarova Saodat Sulaymonovna**
VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY AS A PREDICTOR OF INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY IN CHILDREN WITH ACUTE RHEUMATIC FEVER.....264

37. **Rakhmatullaev Akmal Abadbekovich, Ergashev Mukhammadjon Tursunovich**
EFFECTIVENESS OF ENDOSCOPIC CORRECTION METHODS IN CHILDREN WITH
PRIMARY HIGH-GRADE VESICoureTERAL REFLUX.....275
38. **Akhmedzhanova Nargiza Ismailovna, Ganieva Marifat Shokirovna, Majidova Nilufar
Mansuralievna.** INNOVATIV METHODS OF EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF
TUBULOINTERSTISIAL LESIONS IN ACUTE PYELONEPHRITIS IN CHILD.....281
39. **Terebayev Bilim Aldamuratovich, Barnakulov Umrzok Khasanovich**
PROBLEMS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF DOLICHOSIGMA ASSOCIATED
WITH CHRONIC CONSTIPATION IN CHILDREN.....288
40. **Tilavov Uktam Khamraevich, Chuliev Matyokub Sulaimonovich, Khotamov Khusniddin
Narzullaevich, Abduqodirov Oybek Ahmadjonovich**
DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF CYSTIC ADENOMATOID MALFORMATION OF
THE LUNGS IN CHILDREN.....299
41. **Tukhtaev Firdavs Mukhitdinovich, Kadirov Jonibek Fayzullayevich**
PERSONALIZED METABOLIC APPROACHES IN CHILDREN'S MEDICAL
REHABILITATION.....307
42. **Ibragimova Sapura Zakhidovna, Almedova Nargiza Nigmatjonovna, Botirov Mirzokhid
Mansurzhon Ugli, Shadibekova Oksana Borisovna, Aripova Nazokat Bahodirovna,
Erimbetova Indira Oralbaevna**
RESULTS OF THE USE OF EMICIZUMAB IN PATIENTS WITH HEMOPHILIA A – A
PILOT SINGLE-CENTER STUDY.....312
43. **Khaidarov Khusan Anvarovich**
THE ROLE OF VITAMIN D STATE IN DETERMINING THE SEVERITY AND
EFFECTIVENESS OF INPATIENT TREATMENT OF RECURRENT RESPIRATORY
TRACT INFECTIONS IN YOUNG CHILDREN.....319

SURGERY

44. **Abdurahmonov Ma'mur Mustafaevich, Umedov Xushvaqt Alisherovich,**
ASSESSMENT OF THE IMMUNE SYSTEM STATUS IN ACUTE DESTRUCTIVE
PANCREATITIS.....325
45. **Kurbanov Aslbek Sadullaevich, Arziev Ismoil Alievich, Arzieva Gulnora Borievna**
DIAGNOSTIC AND THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF LAPAROSCOPY IN PATIENTS
WITH BLUNT ABDOMINAL TRAUMA.....331
46. **Yuldashov Parda Arzikulovich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich, Sayinaev Farrukh
Karamatovich**
OPTIMIZATION OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF POSTOPERATIVE VENTRAL
HERNIAS BASED ON LAPAROSCOPIC PROSTHETIC METHODS.....336
47. **Kurbanova Sanobar Yuldashevna, Kamalov Zainitdin Saifutdinovich, Azizova Zukhra
Shukhratovna**
CLINICAL, IMMUNOLOGICAL, AND IMMUNOGENETIC FEATURES OF DISEASE
DEVELOPMENT IN ADULT PATIENTS WITH PYELONEPHRITIS (A LITERATURE
REVIEW).....346
48. **Umedov Xushvaqt Alisherovich, Abdurahmonov Ma'mur Mustafaevich**
CONTEMPORARY CLINICO-MORPHOLOGICAL CLASSIFICATION OF ACUTE
PANCREATITIS AND ITS COMPLICATIONS.....355
49. **Ollabergenov Odilbek Tozhiddinovich, Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich, Parpiev
Mirziyod Mirsaitovich**
CURRENT TRENDS IN THE DIAGNOSIS AND SURGICAL TREATMENT OF LIVER
ECHINOCOCCOSIS IN CHILDREN.....362

50. **Askarov Pulat Azadovich, Bazarov Bahrom Boymamatovich, Kurbaniyazov Zafar Babadjanovich**
THE IMPACT OF CONCOMITANT SURGICAL PATHOLOGY ON THE OUTCOMES OF SIMULTANEOUS OPERATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH VENTRAL HERNIAS AND MORBID OBESITY.....369
51. **Egamberdiev Abdukahhor Abduqodirovich, Arzieva Gulnora Borievna**
ASSESSMENT OF CLINICAL OUTCOMES AND TECHNICAL FEATURES OF ENDOVIDEOSURGICAL TREATMENT OF HIATAL HERNIA.....377
52. **Madazimov Madamin Muminovich, Turaev Feruz Fakhtullayevich, Kiziun Yana Viktorovna, Pustovetova Maria Gennadievna, Akramova Nozima Akramovna, Kiyamov Azizbek Utkirovich**
STUDY OF BREAST BLOOD SUPPLY USING DUPLEX ULTRASOUND IN REDUCTION MAMMOPLASTY.....385

INFECTIOUS DISEASE

53. **Imamov Otabek Sunnatovich, Mahmudov Sherzod Xasanovich, Djumaev Normurod Davlatovich, Bakhodirova Shahlo Bahoriddinovna, Tokhtayev Gairatillo Shukhratillo ugli.**
THE IMPORTANCE OF TEMPERATURE IN THE ETIOLOGY AND MODERN LABORATORY DIAGNOSTICS OF DERMATOMYCOSIS.....394
54. **Imamov Otabek Sunnatovich, Mahmudov Sherzod Xasanovich, Djumaev Normurod Davlatovich, Ernazarova Feruzabonu Ravshanbekovna, Tokhtayev Gairatillo Shukhratillo ugli**
MODERN ETIOLOGICAL SPECTRUM OF DERMATOMYCOSIS PATHOGENS IN THE TASHKENT REGION.....403
55. **Yusupov Mashrab Ismatillovich**
GUT MICROBIOTA: CORRELATION OF PHYSICAL LOAD, DIET, AND HEAT EXCHANGE.....409
56. **Faizullaev Sherzod Kobiljon ugli, Shakharov Dilshod Zhura ugli, Tukhtaev Shohzod Eshmurod ugli, Khuzhamberdiev Sodikjon Uchkun ugli, Samibaeva Umida Khurshidovna**
FEATURES OF THE CLINICAL PICTURE OF THE NEW CORONAVIRUS INFECTION (COVID-19).....420
57. **Samibaeva Umida Khurshidovna, Faizullaev Sherzod Kobiljon ugli, Shakharov Dilshod Zhura ugli, Tukhtaev Shohzod Eshmurod ugli, Khuzhamberdiev Sodikjon Uchkun ugli**
EVALUATION OF THE CLINICAL EFFICACY OF GLYCYRRHIZIC ACID IN PATIENTS WITH COVID-19.....435
58. **Samibaeva Umida Khurshidovna, Faizullaev Sherzod Kobiljon ugli, Shakharov Dilshod Zhura ugli, Tukhtaev Shohzod Eshmurod ugli, Khuzhamberdiev Sodikjon Uchkun ugli**
EVALUATION OF THE CLINICAL EFFICACY OF GLYCYRRHIZIC ACID IN PATIENTS WITH COVID-19.....447
59. **Rashidov Zafar Rakhmatullaevich**
CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF DOPLEROGRAPHY IN THE DETECTION AND MONITORING OF RENAL TUBERCULOSIS.....453

OPHTHALMOLOGY

60. **Nazirova Zulfiya Rustamovna, Turakulova Dilfuza Mukhitdinovna, Khamrayev Shakhruh Ilkhom ugli.**
SURGICAL TREATMENT OF CONGENITAL AND ACQUIRED CATARACTA IN CHILDREN: ANALYSIS OF MODERN METHODS AND STAGES.....460

61. **Turakulova Dilfuza Mukhitdinovna, Nazirova Zulfiya Rustamovna, Axrorova Malika Nosir qizi.**
ANALYSIS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF INTRAOCULAR LENS SUBLUCATION IN CHILDREN.....470
62. **Iskandarova Shakhnoza Tulkinovna, Miralimova Malika Mukhammadovna, Yangiyeva Nodira Rakhimovna**
ASSESSMENT OF THE INFORMATIVE VALUE OF PARENTAL QUESTIONNAIRES IN THE EARLY DETECTION OF REFRACTIVE DISORDERS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN.....477

NEUROSURGERY

63. **Asadov Khamidulla Fatkhullaevich, Okhunov Alisher Oripovich, Asadov Khumoyun Hamidullaevich.**
A NERVE-SPARING ENDOSCOPIC TUNNEL TECHNIQUE FOR THE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF CHRONIC OCCIPITAL MIGRAINE.....485
64. **Okhunov Alisher Oripovich, Asadov Khamidulla Fatkhullaevich, Asadov Khumoyun Hamidullaevich.**
STRATEGY FOR SELECTING THE EXTENT AND STAGING OF SURGICAL TREATMENT IN COMBINED FORMS OF CHRONIC MIGRAINE.....492

UDC: 616.89-008.454:613.83-056.83:364.4

TURAEV Bobir Temirpulotovich

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), associate professor
Samarkand State Medical University

SULTANOV Shoxrux Khabibullaevich

Doctor of Medical Sciences (DSc), associate professor
Tashkent State Medical University

**FACTORS INFLUENCING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MEDICAL AND SOCIAL
REHABILITATION IN PATIENTS WITH CHEMICAL ADDICTIVE DISORDERS
(LITERATURE REVIEW)**

For citation: Turaev T. Bobir, Sultanov Kh. Shoxrux. Factors influencing the effectiveness of medical and social rehabilitation in patients with chemical addictive disorders. Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2026, vol. 11, issue 1.

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18519662>

ANNOTATION

Chemical addictive disorders are currently recognized as one of the most pressing medical and social issues in global healthcare. Psychoactive substance dependence adversely affects not only the physical and mental health of individuals but also their ability to reintegrate into social life. The success of the comprehensive rehabilitation process depends on numerous factors, among which the presence and intensity of risk factors play a crucial role. Analysis based on various scientific sources reveals that biological, psychological, social, and environmental factors significantly influence the effectiveness of the rehabilitation process. In particular, genetic predisposition, early exposure to substance use, psychological instability, family neglect, and lack of social support are among the key contributors that increase the risk of relapse.

Keywords: Chemical addictive disorders, psychoactive substance dependence, risk factors, medical and social rehabilitation, risk of relapse.

TURAYEV Bobir Temirpulotovich

Falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), dotsent
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti

SULTANOV Shoxrux Xabibullayevich

Tibbiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Toshkent davlat tibbiyot universiteti

**KIMYOVIIY ADDIKTIV BUZILISHLAR MAVJUD BO'LGAN BEMORLARDA TIBBIY-
IJTIMOIY REABILITATSIYASI SAMARADORLIGIGA TA'SIR KO'RSATUVCHI XAVF
OMILLAR (ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI)**

ANNOTATSIYA

Kimyoviy addiktiv buzilishlar bugungi kunda global sog'liqni saqlash sohasining eng dolzarb tibbiy-ijtimoiy muammolardan biri sifatida e'tirof etilmoqda. Psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlik inson organizmining nafaqat jismoniy va ruhiy salomatligiga, balki uning ijtimoiy hayotga moslashuvi darajasiga ham salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Kompleks rehabilitatsiya jarayonining muvaffaqiyatlilik darajasi ko'plab omillar bilan bog'liq bo'lib, ayniqsa xavf omillarining mavjudligi va ularning intensivligi muhim rol o'ynaydi. Turli manbalardagi ilmiy ma'lumotlar asosida olib borilgan tahlillar shuni ko'rsatadiki, biologik, psixologik, ijtimoiy va ekologik omillar ushbu rehabilitatsiya jarayonining samaradorligiga sezilarli darajada ta'sir qiladi. Jumladan, genetik moyillik, erta yoshda boshlangan qabul tajribasi, ruhiy nomutanosibliklar, oilaviy befarqlik va ijtimoiy ko'mak yetishmovchiligi retsidiv xavfini oshiruvchi muhim omillar qatoriga kiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: kimyoviy addiktiv buzilishlar, psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlik, xavf omillari, tibbiy-ijtimoiy rehabilitatsiya, retsidiv xavfi.

ТУРАЕВ Бобир Темирпулотович

кандидат медицинских наук (PhD), доцент

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

СУЛТАНОВ Шохрух Хабибуллаевич

доктор медицинских наук (DSc), доцент

Ташкентский государственный медицинский университет

ФАКТОРЫ РИСКА, ВЛИЯЮЩИЕ НА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ МЕДИЦИНСКО-СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ РЕАБИЛИТАЦИИ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ХИМИЧЕСКИМИ АДДИКТИВНЫМИ РАССТРОЙСТВАМИ (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ)

АННОТАЦИЯ

Химические аддиктивные расстройства в настоящее время признаются одной из самых актуальных медицинско-социальных проблем в глобальном здравоохранении. Зависимость от психоактивных веществ оказывает негативное влияние не только на физическое и психическое здоровье человека, но и на уровень его социальной адаптации. Успешность комплексного процесса реабилитации зависит от множества факторов, при этом особую роль играют наличие факторов риска и степень их выраженности. Анализ научных данных из различных источников показывает, что биологические, психологические, социальные и экологические факторы существенно влияют на эффективность процесса реабилитации. В частности, генетическая предрасположенность, ранний опыт употребления, психические дисфункции, семейное равнодушие и недостаточная социальная поддержка относятся к числу значимых факторов, повышающих риск рецидива.

Ключевые слова: химическое аддиктивное расстройство, зависимость от психоактивных веществ, факторы риска, медико-социальная реабилитация, риск рецидива.

Kirish. Psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlik bugungi kunda global jahon miqyosda inson salomatligi va ijtimoiy barqarorligiga jiddiy tahdid solayotgan muhim tibbiy-ijtimoiy muammolardan biri sifatida e'tirof etilmoqda. Ushbu holat nafaqat alohida shaxsning jismoniy va ruhiy holatiga, balki butun jamiyatga, uning iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy va madaniy tizimlariga ham salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Oxirgi o'n yilliklar davomida kimyoviy addiktiv buzilishlar psixoaktiv moddalarni suiiste'mol qilish holatlari nafaqat rivojlangan davlatlarda, balki rivojlanayotgan mintaqalarda ham keskin ortib bormoqda [7,9].

Jahon sog'liqni saqlash tashkiloti tomonidan taqdim etilgan so'nggi statistik ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, dunyo bo'yicha 35 yoshgacha bo'lgan har 20 nafar kishidan kamida bir nafari hayoti davomida biror turdagi psixoaktiv modda - bu alkogol, opioidlar, kannabinoidlar, psixostimulyatorlar yoki boshqa markaziy asab tizimiga ta'sir qiluvchi moddalardan foydalanishni boshlagan. Ulardan taxminan 13-15 foizida esa ushbu holat surunkali qaramlik ravishda suiiste'mol qilish shaklida

o'tgan, bu esa murakkab psixofiziologik buzilishlar, jamiyatdan yakkalanish, jinoyatchilikning rivojlanishi va nogironlik holatlari xavfini oshishiga olib keladi [3,6,11].

Adabiyotlarda keltirilgan turli mintaqaviy ko'rsatkichlar ham bu muammoning qamrovi keng ekanligini tasdiqlaydi. Masalan, Yevropa mamlakatlarida psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlik darajasi umumiy aholi orasida 18-20 foizni tashkil etsa, AQShda ushbu ko'rsatkich 22 foizgacha yetadi. Bunday o'sish dinamikasi ayniqsa yoshlar va o'smirlar orasida sezilarli darajada yuqori bo'lib, ular orasida psixoaktiv moddalarni erta sinab ko'rish holatlari va shundan kelib chiqadigan ruhiy va somatik asoratlar ko'p uchramoqda [1,8].

O'zbekiston Respublikasida ushbu muammo bo'yicha rasmiy statistik ma'lumotlar yetarlicha keng yoritilmagan bo'lsa-da, sog'liqni saqlash muassasalari, psixiatrik va narkologik dispanserlar tomonidan olib borilgan kuzatuvlar psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlik holatlari soni yildan-yilga ortayotganini ko'rsatmoqda. Xususan, so'nggi yillarda qaramlikning yoshga doir chegarasi pasayib borayotgani, ya'ni 16-18 yoshdagi bemorlar sonining ko'paygani alohida xavotir uyg'otmoqda [3,5,12].

Kimyoviy addiktiv buzilishlar yani psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlik o'z navbatida chuqur psixologik va psixiatrik muammolarni yuzaga chiqaradi. Jumladan, xavotirli va depressiv buzilish holatlari, impulsiv harakatlarni nazorat qilishdagi buzilishlar, shuningdek, shaxsiyat buzilishlari tez-tez uchrab turadi. Bundan tashqari, Psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlik organizmda turli somatik kasalliklar - yurak-qon tomir tizimi, jigar, buyrak, nafas yo'llari va oshqozon-ichak traktining surunkali kasalliklari rivojlanishiga sabab bo'ladi. Ayrim hollarda immun tizimi susayishi, yuqumli kasalliklarga (masalan, gepatitlar, OITS) chalinish xavfini ortishiga olib keladi [2,5,9].

Shuni alohida ta'kidlash kerakki, psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlik insonni asta-sekin jamiyatdan ajralishiga, ijtimoiy faollik pasayishiga, atrofdagilar bilan sog'lom munosabatlar o'rnatish qobiliyatining yo'qolishiga olib keladi [7].

Reabilitatsiya markazlari va klinik kuzatuvlar ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, kimyoviy addiktiv buzilishlarga chalingan shaxslar orasida hayotdan umid uzish, ma'naviy bo'shliqlar mavjudligi va mavjudlikdan norozilik hissi ancha yuqori bo'ladi. Bunday psixologik holat o'z navbatida noxush oqibatlariga, xususan, o'z joniga qasd qilishga urinishlar sonining ortishiga sabab bo'ladi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, Psixoaktiv moddalarga qaram bemorlar orasida suitsidal xatti-harakatlar uchrash chastotasi umumiy aholi o'rtasidagi o'rtacha darajadan 5-8 barobar yuqori. Bu holat, ayniqsa, og'ir depressiv epizodlar, ruhiy buzilishlar va motivatsion inqirozlar mavjud bemorlarda kuchliroq namoyon bo'ladi. Bunga qo'shimcha ravishda, ijtimoiy yolg'izlik, moliyaviy inqiroz, ish va turar joydan ayrilish, bularning barchasi suitsid xavfini yanada kuchaytiruvchi omillar sifatida namoyon bo'ladi [1,7,13].

Kimyoviy addiktiv buzilishlarga chalingan bemorlar uchun kompleks tibbiy-ijtimoiy reabilitatsiya - bu ko'p bosqichli, o'zaro bog'liq va uzviy kechuvchi tadbirlar tizimidir. Mazkur jarayon nafaqat organizmni detoksikatsiya qilish yoki giyohvandlikdan voz kechish kabi tibbiy choralarni, balki bemorning ruhiy holatini tiklash, ijtimoiy hayotga moslashtirish, kasbiy va oilaviy integratsiyasini ta'minlash, hayot sifatini yaxshilash va qayta retsidiylarning oldini olishga qaratilgan keng qamrovli profilaktik yondashuvlarni ham o'z ichiga oladi [6,12].

Biroq bu reabilitatsiya jarayonining muvaffaqiyati ko'plab tashqi va ichki omillar bilan chambarchas bog'liqdir. Ayniqsa, bemorning individual psixologik xususiyatlari, mavjud psixiatrik buzilishlari, oilaviy holati, ijtimoiy qo'llab-quvvatlash darajasi va yashash muhitining sifati asosiy rol o'ynaydi. Bu omillarning ko'pchiligi reabilitatsiya jarayoniga ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi asosiy xavf omillari sifatida baholanadi [4,5,14].

Shuningdek, bemorning motivatsiyasi past bo'lsa, reabilitatsiya dasturlariga bo'lgan ishonchi yetarli darajada shakllanmagan bo'lsa yoki u doimiy stressli muhitda bo'lsa, natijalar reabilitatsiya samaradorligi past bo'lishi mumkin. Ba'zan esa bemorlar ijtimoiy stigmatizatsiya, diskriminatsiya yoki huquqiy cheklovlar sababli zarur ijtimoiy resurslardan foydalana olmaydi. Bu holatlar reabilitatsiya samaradorligini keskin pasaytiradi va kasallikning qaytalanish xavfini oshiradi [11,15].

Adabiyotlar tahlili asosida kimyoviy addiktiv buzilish holatlarida kompleks tibbiy-ijtimoiy reabilitatsiya jarayonining samaradorligiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi omillar bir nechta asosiy

guruhlarga ajratiladi. Ulardan eng muhimlaridan biri - bu biologik omillardir. Ushbu omillar bemorning individual fiziologik xususiyatlari, irsiy omillar va markaziy asab tizimidagi funksional o'zgarishlar bilan bevosita bog'liq bo'lib, rehabilitatsiya jarayonining murakkablashishiga olib keladi [7,9,13].

Eng avvalo, biologik omillardan genetik moyillik omilini alohida ta'kidlash lozim. Tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, agar birinchi darajadagi qarindoshlarda (ota-onalar, opa-singillar yoki aka-ukalar) qaramlik holatlari aniqlangan bo'lsa, unda bu shaxsda psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlikka chalinish xavfi umumiy populyatsiyaga nisbatan 3-4 barobar yuqori bo'ladi. Bu holat shuni anglatadiki, ayrim shaxslar tug'ma genetik zaiflik asosida bu patologik holatga nisbatan ko'proq moyillikka ega bo'lishadi [2,8,15].

Shuningdek, neyrobiologik o'zgarishlar ham psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlikda muhim biologik xavf omillaridan biridir. Psixoaktiv moddalar ta'sirida ayniqsa miya dopamin tizimida muvozanat buzilishi kuzatiladi. Dopamin - bu miyadagi "rag'batlantirish" tizimining markaziy elementi bo'lib, motivatsiya, zavq, xursandchilik va harakatlantiruvchi kuchlarni boshqaradi. Qaramlik rivojlanganda bu tizimda yuzaga kelgan o'zgarishlar natijasida bemor tabiiy lazzatlanish manbalariga (masalan, ijtimoiy aloqa, ish faoliyati, oilaviy munosabatlar) nisbatan befarq bo'lib qoladi va faqat psixoaktiv moddalar orqali qisqa muddatli qoniqish his qiladigan holatga tushadi. Ushbu neyrobiologik o'zgarishlar esa rehabilitatsiya jarayonida motivatsion pasayishga, davolash va ijtimoiy ko'maklashuvga nisbatan sust munosabatga sabab bo'ladi [4,7,16].

Kimyoviy addiktiv buzilishlarga chalingan bemorlarning rehabilitatsiya jarayoniga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadigan asosiy xavf omillaridan biri sifatida alohida e'tiborga loyiqdir. Bu omillar, odatda, shaxsning individual ruhiy tuzilishi, ichki emotsional muvozanati, ruhiy salomatlik holati va stressga nisbatan chidamlilik darajasi bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'ladi [9].

Bemorlarning shaxsiy xususiyatlari rehabilitatsiya jarayonining murakkabligiga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlikka chalingan ko'plab shaxslarda impulsivlik (ya'ni harakatlarini oldindan o'ylamasdan bajarish), hissiy beqarorlik, qaror qabul qilishdagi sustkashlik va o'z-o'zini baholash darajasining pasayganligi kabi belgilarga tez-tez duch kelinadi. Aynan past o'zini qadrlash hissi bemorlarni doimiy ravishda o'zini inkor qilish, umidsizlik va befoyda hayot tarzini davom ettirishga majbur qiladi, bu esa rehabilitatsiya samaradorligini keskin pasaytiradi [6,11,15].

Bundan tashqari, psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlik ko'pincha boshqa ruhiy buzilishlar bilan komorbidlikda kechadi. Xususan, statistik ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, qaram bemorlarning 40-60 foizigacha bo'lgan qismida xavotirli-depressiv buzilish holatlari aniqlanadi. Bunday hollarda bemor faqatgina qaramlik bilan emas, balki bir vaqtning o'zida depressiya, xavotirli hamda uyqu buzilishlari va boshqa psixopatologik simptomlar bilan ham kurashishga majbur bo'ladi. Bu esa rehabilitatsiya choralari bo'lgan javobni susaytiradi, motivatsiyani pasaytiradi va bemorning psixoterapevtik yordamlarga bo'lgan ishonchini kamaytiradi [11,17].

Yana bir muhim psixologik omil bu - stressga nisbatan past bardoshlilikdir. psixoaktiv moddalarga qaram bemorlarning ko'pchiligida kundalik hayotdagi stress omillariga (masalan, oilaviy muammolar, ishsizlik, ijtimoiy bosim) bardosh berish qobiliyati juda past bo'ladi. Bu holatlarda bemor stressni yengillashtirish vositasi sifatida yana psixoaktiv moddalarga murojaat qiladi va natijada retsivid holatlar yuzaga keladi. Rehabilitatsiya jarayonida stressga bardoshlilikni oshirishga qaratilgan psixoterapevtik yondashuvlar yetarlicha amalga oshirilmasa, natijadorlik sezilarli darajada pasayadi [4,9,13].

Ijtimoiy omillar ham psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlikka chalingan bemorlarning rehabilitatsiya jarayoniga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadigan muhim tashqi omillardan biri hisoblanadi. Bu omillar bemorning oilaviy muhiti, ijtimoiy munosabatlar doirasi, iqtisodiy holati va ijtimoiy qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimining mavjudligi bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'lib, tiklanish jarayonining ijobiy yoki salbiy tomonga o'zgarishida asosiy rol o'ynaydi [11].

Avvalo, noto'g'ri oilaviy muhit psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlikning shakllanishi va mustahkamlanishida hal qiluvchi omillardan biridir. Bemor bolaligidan mehr-muhabbat yetishmasligi, ota-onaning doimiy janjallari, zo'ravonlik holatlari, e'tiborsizlik yoki haddan tashqari

qattiqqo'lik muhitida ulg'aygan bo'lsa, bu holatlar ruhiy rivojlanishga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi va stressga nisbatan himoyasizlikni kuchaytiradi. Bunday shaxslar psixoaktiv moddalardan vaqtincha "xaloskor" sifatida foydalanishga intiladi, bu esa oxir-oqibatda chuqur qaramlikka olib keladi. Reabilitatsiya davrida esa, agar bemor yana salbiy oilaviy sharoitga qaytsa, bu uning davolanishga bo'lgan motivatsiyasini pasaytiradi va retsivlanish (qaytalanish) ehtimolini oshiradi [8,14,17].

Shuningdek, atrof-muhit va do'stlar ta'siri ayniqsa o'smirlar va yoshlik davridagi shaxslarda juda katta ahamiyatga ega. Psixoaktiv moddalarni suiiste'mol qiladigan do'stlar guruhiga qo'shilish, salbiy ijtimoiy me'yorlar hukmron bo'lgan muhitda yashash yoki ijtimoiy bosim ostida qolish kishi ongida psixoaktiv moddalarni "qochish yo'li" sifatida qabul qilishiga sabab bo'ladi. Bu esa nafaqat qaramlikka olib keladi, balki davolanish jarayonida ham ijtimoiy qo'llab-quvvatlovning yo'qligi sababli ijobiy natijalar sustlashadi. Shu boisdan, reabilitatsiya jarayonida atrof-muhitni sog'lomlashtirish va salbiy ijtimoiy aloqalarni cheklash muhim strategik vazifa hisoblanadi [9,16].

Yana bir muhim omil bu - ishsizlik va ijtimoiy beqarorlikdir. Mehnat bilan bandlikning yo'qligi, iqtisodiy qiyinchiliklar, doimiy daromad manbasining mavjud emasligi psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlik xavfini oshiradi. Ishsiz shaxslar ko'pincha vaqtini mazmunsiz o'tkazishga majbur bo'ladi, bu esa psixoaktiv moddalarga murojaat qilish imkoniyatini oshiradi. Bunday shaxslar o'zini jamiyatda keraksizdek his qiladi, ijtimoiy izolyatsiya kuchayadi, psixologik beqarorlik vujudga keladi. Buning natijasida reabilitatsiya jarayonida motivatsiya zaiflashadi, ijtimoiy moslashuv sekinlashadi. Shu boisdan reabilitatsiya jarayonining muhim tarkibiy qismi sifatida kasbiy reabilitatsiya, ishga joylashtirish, ijtimoiy rollarni tiklash kabi yo'nalishlar kiritilishi lozim [6,8,13].

Ekologik omillar psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlikning shakllanishi, rivojlanishi va reabilitatsiya jarayonining natijadorligiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadigan tashqi muhit bilan bog'liq omillar qatoriga kiradi. Bu omillar odam yashaydigan hududning ekologik holati, psixoaktiv moddalarga kirish imkoniyati va turmush sharoitlari bilan chambarchas bog'liqdir. Eng avvalo, yashash joyining ijtimoiy va ekologik xususiyatlari muhim rol o'ynaydi. Aholining zich yashaydigan, ekologik jihatdan noqulay bo'lgan yoki jinoyatchilik darajasi yuqori bo'lgan hududlarda psixoaktiv moddalarning noqonuniy aylanishi ko'proq uchraydi. Bunday joylarda turmush tarzi odatda past bo'lib, yoshlar va o'smirlar uchun salbiy ijtimoiy namunalar keng tarqalgan bo'ladi. Bundan tashqari, sog'lom madaniy-ko'ngilochar infratuzilmaning yo'qligi, ijtimoiy nazoratning sustligi va ish bilan bandlikning past darajasi psixoaktiv moddalardan foydalanish xavfini orttiradi [3,7,11,16].

Psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlikning shakllanishida yoshlik davrida duch kelish holatlari, oilaviy muhit va ijtimoiy qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimi yetishmovchiligi muhim xavf omillari sifatida ajralib turadi. Tadqiqotlar natijasiga ko'ra, psixotrop moddalarga erta, ya'ni 14-17 yosh oralig'ida duch kelgan shaxslarda psixoaktiv moddalarga nisbatan barqaror psixologik va fiziologik qaramlik shakllanish xavfi deyarli 70 foizga yaqin bo'ladi. Bu holat o'smirlar davrida shaxsning ongli qaror qabul qilish qobiliyati hali to'liq shakllanmaganligi, emotsional beqarorlik va tashqi ta'sirlarga bo'lgan yuqori sezuvchanlik bilan bog'liq [11,14,18].

Shuningdek, oilaviy beqarorlik, uyda mavjud zo'ravonlik holatlari, psixologik yoki jismoniy e'tiborsizlik psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlikka olib boruvchi asosiy ijtimoiy omillar qatoriga kiradi. Kuzatishlarga ko'ra, qaramlik bilan davolanayotgan bemorlarning 60-75 foizi beqaror oilaviy sharoitda ulg'aygan yoki shunday muhitda yashashda davom etmoqda. Bunday muhitda o'sgan shaxslar ko'pincha hissiy bo'shliqni to'ldirish, tashvish yoki ruhiy og'riqni yengillash tirish maqsadida psixoaktiv moddalardan foydalanishga urinadilar. Afsuski, bu urinishlar ko'pincha surunkali qaramlik holatiga olib keladi [3,5,9,14].

Ijtimoiy qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimining zaifligi ham reabilitatsiya samaradorligini sezilarli darajada pasaytiradi. Ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, bemorning ijtimoiy himoyasi yoki yaqinlarining doimiy emotsional yordami mavjud bo'lmagan holatlarda qayta qaramlik (retsiv) rivojlanish ehtimoli ikki baravar ortadi. Bu holat psixoaktiv moddadan voz kechish yo'lida yakkalanib qolgan shaxslarning zaif emotsional holatini aks ettirib, ularning tiklanishdagi muvaffaqiyatsizlikka uchrash xavfini kuchaytiradi [6,9,17].

Shu bilan birga, kompleks yondashuv asosidagi reabilitatsiya dasturlarining samaradorligi yuqori baholanmoqda. Ayniqsa, xavf omillari - ya'ni oilaviy muhit, ijtimoiy qo'llab-quvvatlash

darajasi singari omillar tizimli ravishda nazoratga olingan va bartaraf etilgan holatlarda ijobiy natijalar kuzatilmogda. Bunday holatlarda reabilitatsiyaga jalb etilgan bemorlarning 80 foizdan ortig'i davolashga ijobiy javob qaytargan, ular orasida retsivlanish holatlari minimal darajada bo'lgan [7,13].

Ushbu ma'lumotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlik faqat individual tanlov emas, balki ko'plab ijtimoiy, oilaviy va psixologik omillar bilan bog'liq murakkab jarayon bo'lib, uni samarali oldini olish va davolash faqat kompleks yondashuv va ko'p darajali qo'llab-quvvatlash orqali mumkin bo'ladi.

Xulosa. Kimyoviy addiktiv buzilishlarga chalingan shaxslarning tibbiy-ijtimoiy reabilitatsiyasi samaradorligiga ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi xavf omillari orasida erta yoshda psixoaktiv moddalarni sinab ko'rish, oilaviy beqarorlik, psixologik beparvolik, zo'ravonlik holatlari va ijtimoiy qo'llab-quvvatlov yetishmovchiligi alohida o'rin tutadi. Ushbu omillar reabilitatsiya jarayonini murakkablashtirib, qayta qaramlik (retsiv) xavfini oshiradi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, reabilitatsiya samaradorligini oshirish uchun xavf omillarini erta aniqlash, ularni tizimli nazoratga olish va bemorning ijtimoiy muhitini barqarorlashtirish zarur. Shuningdek, kompleks, ko'p bosqichli yondashuv - psixoterapiya, ijtimoiy adaptatsiya, oilaviy maslahat va monitoringni o'z ichiga olgan reabilitatsiya dasturlari ijobiy natija beradi. Demak, samarali reabilitatsiya uchun nafaqat tibbiy, balki ijtimoiy va psixologik omillarni ham to'liq hisobga olish muhim hisoblanadi.

IQTIBOSLAR | SNOSKI | REFERENCES

1. Afanasyev A. L. et al. Drug addiction as a medical, social and psychological problem. Rehabilitation of drug addicts //Психологічні проблеми особистості на сучасному етапі. – 2021. – С. 254.
2. Amel A. K. et al. Effective Interventions for Social-Psychological Rehabilitation in Addiction Recovery: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis //Middle East Journal of Rehabilitation and Health Studies. – 2025. – Т. 12. – №. 12.
3. Delmiati S. et al. Implementation of Medical Rehabilitation and Social Rehabilitation for Addicts and Victims of Drug Abuse //Ekasakti Journal of Law and Justice. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 21-29.
4. Ergashev S. S., Mamurova M. M., Turayev B. T. Clinical-neurophysiological morphological Studies of children with Consequences of hypoxia //Journal of Medical Genetics and Clinical Biology. – 2025. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 117-125.
5. Ibragim A. et al. Psychological rehabilitation of individuals with alcohol use disorder, drug addiction, gambling disorder, and codependency //Acta Psychologica. – 2025. – Т. 257. – С. 105052.
6. Idaiani S. et al. Relapse in Drugs, Psychotropic, Addictive Abuse Post Rehabilitation: "Policy and Prevention Programs" //4th International Symposium on Health Research (ISHR 2019). – Atlantis Press, 2020. – С. 56-59.
7. Konstantinova O. et al. Clinical and psychological characteristics of patients with alcoholism with suicidal behavior //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D11. – С. 399-404.
8. Kuznetsov V. V. Medical rehabilitation of patients with addictive pathology //Neurology Bulletin. – 2015. – Т. 47. – №. 3. – С. 90-98.
9. Lomakin S. et al. Socio-demographic, personal and clinical characteristics of relatives of patients with alcoholism //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 278-283.
10. Murad A. A. A., AL-Sarray A. A. M., Jamal Z. Drug Addiction Clinical Study Among Patients Admitted to the Alqana Center for Social Rehabilitation //South Eastern European Journal of Public Health. – 2024.
11. Novikov A. et al. Alcohol dependence and manifestation of autoaggressive behavior in patients of different types //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D11. – С. 413-419.
12. Ochilov U. et al. Factors of alcoholic delirium patomorphosis //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 223-229.

13. Ochilov U. et al. The question of the features of clinical and immunological parameters in the diagnosis of juvenile depression with "subpsychotic" symptoms //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 218-222.
14. Sedenkova M. et al. The possibility of predicting the time of formation and development of alcohol dependence: the role of genetic risk, family weight and its level //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 173-178.
15. Sultanov S., Turayev B., Xamrakulova K. The clinical characteristics of personality changes in secondary alcoholism //Modern Science and Research. – 2025. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 782-791.
16. Turayev B. Comprehensive rehabilitation for alcoholism: recovery and treatment approaches //Modern Science and Research. – 2025. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 309-319.
17. Zhukova E. C., Leushina E. A. Analysis of risk factors and medical rehabilitation of drug addicts //Молодежный инновационный вестник. – 2024. – Т. 13. – №. S1. – С. 459-462.
18. Щербина С., Новак Т., Гноевой Ю. Social work for the resocialisation of drug addicts in rehabilitation centres //Науковий вісник Ужгородського університету. Серія:«Педагогіка. Соціальна робота». – 2025. – Т. 1. – №. 56. – С. 278-283.
19. Rizaev , Zh., Shomurodov , K., & Agzamova , S. (2022). MEDICAL REHABILITATION OF PATIENTS WITH FRACTURES OF THE ZYKMOGO-ORBITAL COMPLEX. Journal of Dentistry and Craniofacial Research, 1(2), 8–11. <https://doi.org/10.26739.2181-0966-2020-2-1>
20. Inogamov Sh. M., Sadikov A. A., Rizaev Zh. A. METHODS FOR PREVENTION OF DAMAGE TO THE DENTAL APPARATUS AMONG ATHLETES PLAYING CONTACT SPORTS // Biology. – 2021. – No. 1. – P. 125.
21. Raimkulova D.F., Rizaev Zh.A., Sadikov A.A. Assessment of endothelial dysfunction and oxidative stress in athletes of various sports // Problems of biology and medicine. – 2020. – Т. 5. – No. 122. – pp. 109-112.
22. Iroda Nodirovna Maxammatkulova (2021). TEACHING SPEAKING IN ENGLISH LESSONS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS. Academic research in educational sciences, 2 (7), 95-98. doi : 10.24412/2181-1385-2021-7-95-98 17.
23. Maxammatkulova Iroda Nodirovna Game as a method of teaching English in primary school// EDUCATION AND THE SCIENCE IN THE XXI CENTURY.- 2021.-№16.- p . 106-109
24. Maxammatkulova Iroda Nodirovna Chet tilini o'qitishda yangi so'zlarning ahamiyati // Internauka.-2021.-No. 26(206).-P.95-102

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000